

Original Research

Financial Institutions' Development and Economic Growth: Evidence from Sri Lanka by Employing ARDL Model

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Abstract

This research aims to analyse the influence of financial institutions' development on the economic growth of Sri Lanka in both the short and long term, to shed light on the significance of financial institutions in stimulating the economic performance of the country. Data for the study is collected solely from Sri Lanka, utilising annual data from 1963 to 2021. Broad Money, Financial system deposits, Domestic credit to the private sector, and Claims in the Private Sector are used to measure financial depth and financial efficiency which are the indicators of financial institutions' development. Statistical tools such as Unit Root Tests and Co-Integration Tests are employed using the E-Views version six software package. Findings indicate significant positive short-run and long-run impacts of financial institutions' development on economic growth. Although some variables exhibit insignificant results, Broad Money and Claims in the Private Sector emerge as the most influential factors affecting the economic growth of Sri Lanka. The hypothesis adopted in the study can be accepted that there is a supply-leading hypothesis that exists in terms of financial institutions' development and economic growth in Sri Lanka. The Central Bank of Sri Lanka can adopt policies to ease the monetary conditions relating to the lending and depositing facilities of financial institutions. This can induce the Broad Money and the Claims on the Private Sector, and it will stimulate the economic growth of the country as a whole. Thus, this paper sheds light on the specific area on which the country should focus to reconstruct the country from the worst.

Keywords: Banking sector development, Economic growth, Financial development, Financial institutions.

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Introduction

Exploring the influencing factors of economic growth always gets attention, as economic growth is the ultimate objective of every nation globally. Effective resource allocation and increased capital development are two factors that stimulate economic growth (Kumar and Paramanik, 2020). Financial development is vastly associated with economic growth by most econometrics scholars. The association of financial development and growth of the economy has got an immense amount of consideration over the last three decades, and a lot of study has been done in this area. Amarathunga (2012) defines a financial system as consisting of financial institutions (FIs), financial markets, financial instruments, and financial infrastructure, which includes payment and settlement systems and the regulatory framework. Hence, a financial system comprises the financial institutions and financial markets majorly. Economic growth is significantly influenced by financial development. Fathima Rinosha and Mohamed Mustafa (2021) also point out that enhancing economic development through technical advancement, economic growth, innovation, and capital accumulation is crucial. To do this, encourage investment and saving while effectively managing an economy's finances.

The Central Bank of Sri Lanka regulates financial institutions and markets to uphold the financial system, which includes the Banking Sector, Licensed Finance Companies, Specialised Leasing Companies Sector, and Insurance Sector (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2022). Thus, the study targets the development of the financial institutions, particularly with the intention of getting concise results on economic growth. Haini (2020) states that financial development is crucial for fostering economic growth; nevertheless, the impact of financial institutions and financial markets may vary. Moreover, particularly over the last few decades, the expansion of the banking industry's contribution to promoting growth of the economy has drawn considerable attention and served as the subject of numerous theoretical and empirical research (King and Levine, 1993); (Pagano, 1993); (Levine, 2005); (Ang, 2008). Meanwhile, one school of thought maintains that assessing the effect of credit and stock markets on economic growth is unattainable (Beck and Levine, 2004). Aside from that, excluding stock market development complicates the justification of whether a favourable long-term effect of banking development on economic growth persists when stock market development is taken into account (Wu, Hou, and Cheng, 2010). However, the researcher argues that more precise and thorough results will be obtained by investigating the relation between the development of financial institutions and the growth of the economy than the previous research studies.

Sri Lanka has undergone a significant decline in economic growth following the spread of COVID-19 and the economic turmoil resulting from political instability. (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2023). Figure 1.1 exhibits the GDP growth rate over the years from 2015 to 2023, shown for each quarter.

Figure 1. GDP Growth rate from 2015 to 2023
Source: (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2023)

It clearly depicts the struggle the country went through after COVID-19 spread; a dramatic decrease in the GDP growth rate continued to 2022. Nevertheless, it shows some improvement in the current quarters of the current year 2023. Besides, the country is also showing signals of reviving from the financial crisis, as evidenced by the reduction in inflation and increase in the money value against the dollar rate. As per the (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2023), after experiencing its worst economic disaster the year before, the Sri Lankan economy started to recover in 2023. It reflects the reviving stage of the country. According to (World Bank, 2023), assets held by the financial industry totaled Rs. 23,704 billion in 2021, or 141% of GDP. The statistics indicate that the financial system is one of the most prominent and crucial sectors in Sri Lanka. Therefore, identifying the importance of financial institutions' development at this reviving stage would benefit the regulators to enhance the growth of the economy. Although the Central Bank of Sri Lanka is continuously supervising and regulating financial institutions, this research will provide a clear idea of focusing on the specialised area that the development of financial institutions and economic growth are statistically dependent on. Besides, analysing both the long-run and short-run impact of the development of financial institutions on economic growth will enhance the clarity of taking the actions that mitigate the current economic crisis in a certain time frame. The current research also will have significant importance among the research practitioners since the study explores the most prominent sector in Sri Lanka, which is the sector of the financial institution. The sector development is going to be analysed with economic growth, which should be analysed to improve from the worst situation. Thus, the current research intends to analyse the influence of financial institutions' development on economic growth in Sri Lanka with the organisation of a literature review, methodology, results, and conclusion.

Literature review

Theoretical association between financial institutions' development and economic growth

According to certain economists, attaining a high degree of economic growth requires the development of the financial sector. Such economists are: (Goldsmith, 1969); (McKinnon, 1973); (Shaw, 1973). Economists today have a better understanding of the nature and relationship between financial systems and economic growth. The role of the financial sector in economic development has received increased attention from scholars and decision-makers (Ndikumana, 2003), and as a result, opposing viewpoints have emerged. An increasing amount of empirical research has shown a substantial positive relationship between the efficient functioning of the financial system and the long-term growth of the economy. These research studies have included organisation-wise studies, sector-wise studies, single country studies, and extensive comparisons via cross-countries (Levine, 1997). The most attractive study by Goldsmith (1969) showed a positive relationship between financial development and GDP per capita for the first time, utilising a yearly data set of 35 countries from 1860 to 1963. Later, Levine (1997) identifies five fundamental tasks that make up a financial system's functions: Financial systems 1) facilitate the trading, hedging, diversifying, and pooling of risk; 2) allocate resources; 3) monitor managers and exert corporate control; 4) mobilise savings; and 5) facilitate the exchange of goods and services. However, on the contrary, Levine (2005) started his review article with "Economists disagree sharply about the role of the financial sector in economic growth." Citing other articles, he critically reviewed how other scholars argued. The concept of the relation between finance and growth may be easily disregarded without significantly affecting our comprehension of economic growth. The uncertainty should yet be scientifically examined and addressed. As a result, this research will clarify the ambiguity of employing empirical data in the Sri Lankan setting. Sri Lanka is a lower middle-income country, and still it is being developed. In addition to that, Sri Lanka had a severe fluctuation in GDP growth over these years due to various external factors, such as local war, political instability, the Easter attack, and COVID-19. Thus, the financial development theory is in question for a developing country that had a severe fluctuation in economic growth.

Empirical Association between financial institutions' development and economic growth

Patrick (1966) named the first supply-leading hypothesis. He referred to the "supply-leading" role of financial development in economic growth in the five ways. Later, various scholars performed empirical evidence to support the supply-leading hypothesis. Studies covering the Asian countries are large in number. An important article among those is by (Ahmed and Ansari, 1998), which investigated the relationship between the expansion of the financial sector and the economic expansion of India, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka—the three biggest South Asian nations. Standard Granger causality tests are employed to evaluate the pattern of causal relationship between different financial sector development indicators and economic growth. The results of causality analysis show that economic growth is driven by the expansion of the financial sector. This validates the supply-led hypothesis.

A recent article by (Haini, 2020) also investigated the Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) economies using a dynamic panel estimator to examine how financial and institutional change affected economic growth between 1995 and 2017. The findings indicate that while financial markets are negligible, financial institutions contribute

significantly and favourably to economic growth. The other article (Chee and Nair, 2010) used panel data methods (fixed effects estimator and random effects estimator) to analyse the link between FDI, financial sector development, and economic growth in the Asia-Oceania area. The empirical investigation's findings showed that FDI's contribution to regional economic growth increases as the banking sector develops. It also implied that the region's least developed economies most urgently require the additional benefits of foreign direct investment and the expansion of the finance sector for economic growth. Besides, (Guru and Yadav, 2019) undertook a study to investigate, from 1993 to 2014, the relationship between financial development and economic growth using stock market indices and the banking industry for the five major emerging economies that make up the BRICS group: China, India, South Africa, Russia, and Brazil. A number of the most important macroeconomic and financial development gauges of the chosen economies have also been employed. Findings showed that each of the chosen indices of banking development, such as the size of financial intermediaries, CDR, and CPS, are positively significantly determining economic growth.

From the perspective of African countries, Anarfo et al. (2019) contributed to the theory using the data from World Development Indicators covering the years 1990–2014 for 48 Sub-Saharan African economies and 217 global economies for the entire sample. The authors aim to advance theory by establishing the tripartite relationship among financial inclusion, financial sector development, and economic growth from the Sub-Saharan Africa perspective. Based on the results of the entire sample, researchers came to the conclusion that the rise of the financial sector is another important factor driving economic expansion. The whole sample's results demonstrated a tripartite relationship between economic growth, financial sector development, and financial inclusion. The other article of Puatwoe and Piabuo (2017) has undertaken an article titled "Financial sector development and economic growth: evidence from Cameroon," which investigated the impact of financial development on Cameroon's economic growth using time series data. This study employed three commonly used indicators of financial development: domestic credit to the private sector, deposit/GDP, and broad money. It was discovered that bank deposits, private investment, and economic growth have an equal and opposing short-term relationship. Additionally, monetary size (M2), government spending, and economic growth have a short-term positive association. However, over the long run, every indication of financial development suggests a positive and noteworthy impact on economic growth.

Further, Durusu-Ciftci, Ispir and Yetkiner (2017) enhanced comprehension of the theoretical and empirical relationships between financial development and economic growth. In the empirical part, the long-term relationship is computed for a panel of 40 countries for the years 1989–2011 using an Augmented Mean Group (AMG) and Common-Correlated Effects (CCE), both of which permit cross-sectional dependencies. The panel data analyses showed that the steady-state level of GDP per capita is positively impacted by both channels over the long term, with the credit markets contributing by a much bigger amount. While Pradhan et al. (2014) investigated the connections between a certain economy's economic growth and the development of its banking industry or between that economy's growth rate and its inflation rate. This paper built on past work by using panel cointegration and causality tests in 34 OECD nations between 1960 and

2011. Findings offer compelling evidence that both inflation and the growth of the banking sector are important for a nation's economy.

Besides, in the Sri Lankan context, Wijesinghe and Pallearachchi (2022) recently published an article aimed at exploring the integral part played by the banking industry in bolstering Sri Lanka's economic expansion by emphasising the immediate and long-term connections between the industry's success and the country's economic expansion. The analysis showed that the banking industry development indicator had a favourable effect on economic growth, indicating long-term support for the supply-led growth paradigm. The results of the Granger Causality test indicated a one-way relationship between GDP growth and banking industry expansion. Addition with, Fathima Rinosha and Mohamed Mustafa (2021) also analysed the long-term relationship between economic expansion and financial development. The study used the Consumer Price Index, Trade, Labor Force, Credit to the Private Sector, and the Ratio of Gross Fixed Capital Formation to GDP as independent variables and the Gross Domestic Product as a dependent variable. Given the statistically strong correlation between financial development and economic growth in the nation, the Sri Lankan government ought to modify its trade policy. Meanwhile, another recent article by Maheswaranathan and Jeewanthi (2021) used the ARDL technique to investigate the relationship between Sri Lanka's economic growth, foreign direct investment, and financial development. The findings indicate a positive long-term relationship between net foreign direct investment inflows and economic expansion. Additionally, FDI, CI, and BCP have a favourable and large short-term influence on GDP.

On the other hand, Patrick (1966) started to term demand-following hypothesis in his article. It is defined as "a process wherein contemporary institutions in the financial system, their economical assets and liabilities, and associated monetary services are created in response to the demand for such services from those who invest and save in the real economy." This phenomenon is known as "demand-following." The research article of (Kaushal and Ghosh, 2016) attempted to explore the link between the growth of the Indian economy and financial institutions. According to the results, there is a long-term correlation between insurance companies and economic growth, and vice versa. It is also discovered that the development of banking institutions is a direct result of economic progress. Concluded that demand, not supply, and is driving the development of India's banking institutions. While the African study of Ndlovu (2013) analysed the causal relationship between the expansion of the economy and the development of the financial system based on two interrelated goals. The first goal was to establish a cointegration relationship between the two and determine the ultimate course of the causal relationship from a Zimbabwean perspective. Using the multivariate Granger causality test, the study demonstrates that demand follows financial development in Zimbabwe and also demonstrates a unilateral causal relationship.

The research articles, which are carried out on the development of financial institutions and the growth of the economy in both foreign and Sri Lankan countries, reflected inconsistencies in the results they found. Many researchers, for instance: (Ahmed and Ansari, 1998); (Haini, 2020); (Chee and Nair, 2010); (Guru and Yadav, 2019); (Anarfo et al., 2019); (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Durusu-Ciftci, Ispir and Yetkiner, 2017); (Pradhan et al., 2014); (Wijesinghe and Pallearachchi, 2022); (Fathima Rinosha and

Mohamed Mustafa, 2021); (Maheswaranathan and Jeewanthi, 2021) have concluded by accepting the supply-led hypothesis. On the contrary, while some researchers, for example: (Patrick, 1966); (Kaushal and Ghosh, 2016); (Ndlovu, 2013) have accepted the demand-led hypothesis, some, for instance (Sunde, 2012); (Adelakun, 2010); (Odeniran and Udejaja, 2010); (Pradhan et al., 2014; (Bhanumurthy and Singh, 2013); (Jahfer and Inoue, 2014) found a bidirectional relation of development of financial institutions and growth in the economy, and very few (for example- (Mazur and Alexander, 2001); (Rexiang and Rathanasiri, 2011); (Perera and Paudel, 2009) have failed to get a significant impact. This is also evidenced by (Durusu-Ciftci, Ispir and Yetkiner, 2017), who stated in their article that the majority of empirical models usually show that robust financial markets improve resource allocation efficiency and accelerate long-term growth through a number of routes. Previous scholarly studies demonstrate the positive and negative relation between the development of financial institutions and growth in the economy. The ambiguity should still be investigated and resolved scientifically. As a result, the objective of this current research will be to provide clarification to the ambiguity by using empirical data in the context of Sri Lanka.

While numerous studies have examined the relation between the development of the financial sector and growth in the economy on a global scale, examples of such research studies are: (Kumar and Paramanik, 2020); (OtcHERE, Senbet and Simbanegavi, 2017); (Odeniran and Udejaja, 2010); (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Ndlovu, 2013). There remains a limited focus on finance and growth within the Sri Lankan context. Examples of such research studies are: (Perera and Madurapperuma, 2020); (Amarathunga, 2012); (Perera and Paudel, 2009); (Fathima Rinosha and Mohamed Mustafa, 2021). Further, many scholars used the OLS technique for the analysis of time series with mixed integrated orders, which depicts there might be the false in the results; thus, the methodological gap has also been identified by the researcher. Moreover, there is a significant empirical gap during the considered period, including the current turbulent situation. This current research aims to analyse the development of financial institutions and their impact on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in an effort to bridge this empirical gap, thereby contributing to the collection of knowledge already in existence.

Data and Methodology

The present study is confined to taking secondary data from the country Sri Lanka and utilised data collection over the yearly data for the period from 1963 to 2021. 58 years have been selected according to the availability of the data and prior to COVID-19 and the crisis to avoid misleading results. The analysis used secondary data sources, namely the Central Bank of Sri Lanka's annual reports and World Bank statistics, to investigate the impact of financial institutions' development and economic growth in Sri Lanka.

According to the literature review, Ofoeda et al. (2022) used a mix of efficiency, accessibility, and depth to measure financial development. Access describes a customer's ability to obtain financial services; efficiency reviews an institution's ability to do so at a cost that is both affordable and sustainable over the long run; and depth evaluates an institution's size and liquidity. Additionally, private-sector credit, pension fund assets, mutual fund assets, and insurance premiums (both life and non-life) to GDP are used to measure the depth of financial institutions, and the number of bank branches and ATMs

per 100,000 adults is used to measure access. Financial institutions' efficiency score is determined by their net interest margin, lending-deposit spread, and non-interest income to total income, overhead costs to total assets, return on equity, and return on assets. Anarfo et al. (2019) employed Domestic credit provided by the financial sector as a percentage of GDP to measure financial sector development. Guru and Yadav (2019) considered the size of financial intermediaries, the credit-to-deposit ratio (CDR), and domestic credit to the private sector (CPS) as indices of the banking industry's development in the study. While Puatwoe and Piabuo (2017) were able to capture financial development by focusing on the depth and efficiency of the Cameroonian financial system. The paper assessed financial depth from two perspectives: broad money, which covers broad money and demand, and financial system deposits, which encompass savings and time deposits, both of which are presented as a percentage of GDP. Broad money (M2/GDP) and financial system deposits (Deposits) are employed as economic and financial sector indicators, while domestic credit to the private sector is utilised as an indicator of financial efficiency. The study of (Chee and Nair, 2010) used the following proxies to gauge the growth of the financial sector: Private credit is the amount of credits given to the private sector by financial intermediaries divided by GDP, and liquid liabilities are the ratio of the financial system's liquid liabilities (often M3, or M2 when M3 is unavailable) to GDP. Pradhan et al. (2014) employed claims on assets, domestic credit given by the banking sector, domestic credit to the private sector, and liquid liabilities to measure the development of the banking industry. Broad money expressed as a proportion of GDP was also used. To analyse the financial sector growth, Ahmed and Ansari (1998) employed three different financial development indicators: the ratios of broad money, quasi-money, and domestic credit to nominal GDP.

In the Sri Lankan context, Rexiang and Rathanasiri (2011) used the proportion of GDP for commercial bank liquid liabilities and credit to the private sector and commercial bank assets as a percentage of GDP to measure the financial intermediation development (FD), the standard indicators used in this study. Fathima Rinosha and Mohamed Mustafa (2021) employed Credit to The Private Sector, the Ratio of the Gross Fixed Capital Formation to GDP, Trade, the Consumer Price Index, and Labor Force to measure Financial Development. Wijesinghe and Dulanjani (2022) measured Development of the financial sector as a percentage of real liabilities each year, which is M3.

Growth of the economy was measured by GDP per capita, or GDP growth, which has been widely adopted as a benchmark by academics for decades. For instance: (Chee and Nair, 2010); (Ndlovu, 2013); (Pradhan et al., 2014); (Jahfer and Inoue, 2014); (Kaushal and Ghosh, 2016); (Guru and Yadav, 2019); (Durusu-Ciftci, Ispir and Yetkiner, 2017); (Anarfo et al., 2019); (Perera and Paudel, 2009); (Maheswaranathan and Jeewanthi, 2021); (Wijesinghe and Dulanjani, 2022).

Table 1. List of variables

Key concept	Variables	Measurement
Independent variable Financial institutions development	Financial depth	The ratio of broad money to nominal per capital GDP. (Wijesinghe and Pallearachchi, 2022); (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Mazur and Alexander, 2001); (Perera and Paudel, 2009).
		Financial system deposits to GDP (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017).
	Financial efficiency	Domestic credit to private sector by banks (% of GDP) (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Sunde, 2012); (Odeniran and Udejaja, 2010); (Mazur and Alexander, 2001). Claims on private sector (annual growth as % of broad money). (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Sunde, 2012); (Odeniran and Udejaja, 2010); (Mazur and Alexander, 2001).
Dependent variable Economic growth	GDP Growth	GDP Growth rate (Wijesinghe and Pallearachchi, 2022); (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Mazur and Alexander, 2001); (Perera and Paudel, 2009).

The World Bank's Global Financial Development Database developed a comprehensive, simple conceptual framework to measure financial development around the world. It includes four dimensions: financial depth, access, efficiency, and stability. The researcher chose two dimensions, namely financial depth and financial efficiency, as dimensions of financial institutions' development based on the previous research studies, which used these two dimensions more widely than others. The variables are presented in the above Table 1.

Hypothesis development

According to the literature review, it is evidenced that according to some economists, depending on financial development is necessary to achieve a high rate of economic growth (Goldsmith, 1969); (McKinnon, 1973); (Shaw, 1973). Besides, an increasing amount of empirical research, including studies conducted at the firm, sector, and national levels as well as thorough cross-national comparisons, has demonstrated a strong positive correlation between the functioning of the financial system and the economy's long-term growth (Levine, 1997). Empirically also, many research scholars are from both internationally and locally. For instance: (Ahmed and Ansari, 1998); (Haini, 2020); (Chee and Nair, 2010); (Guru and Yadav, 2019); (Anarfo et al., 2019); (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Durusu-Ciftci, Ispir and Yetkiner, 2017); (Pradhan et al., 2014); (Wijesinghe and Pallearachchi, 2022); (Fathima Rinosha and Mohamed Mustafa, 2021); (Maheswaranathan and Jeewanthi, 2021) have concluded by accepting the supply-leading

hypothesis rather than demand following and bi-directional Based on the above premise, the following testable hypotheses are proposed:

H₁: There is a supply-leading hypothesis between the development of financial institutions and the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka.

According to the measurements undertaken by previous research scholars, the researcher identified as the first proxy for financial depth is the ratio of liquid liabilities of the financial system to GDP, and it can be stated as broad money (% of GDP). This ratio should be a good indicator of the provision of financial intermediary services (Demirguc-Kunt and Levine, 1996). This is also used by scholars earlier. Such scholars are: (Wijesinghe and Pallearachchi, 2022); (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Mazur and Alexander, 2001); (Perera and Paudel, 2009). The other proxy which depicts financial depth is financial system deposits which are used by (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017). Rousseau and Wachtel (2001) found the depth of the financial sector's strong and reliable impact on economic growth, and Puatwoe and Piabuo (2017) confirmed the substantial and favorable effects of financial system deposits and wide money on economic growth. Besides, Chee and Nair (2010) also concluded their findings that in order for FDI to support economic growth, liquid liabilities/M2 or M3 are essential. This evidence prompted the researcher to formulate the following hypotheses.

- **H_{1a}**: Financial depth has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.
- **H_{1a1}**: Broad money has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.
- **H_{1a2}**: Financial system deposits have a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.

The ability of a financial system to carry out its primary function of converting deposits into credits is a measure of its efficiency (Asongu, 2012). The two measures for financial efficiency that have been chosen for the study include Domestic credit to the private sector by banks (percentage of GDP) and Claims on the private sector (annual growth as percentage of broad money). This has also been used by researchers before. Such researchers are: (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Sunde, 2012); (Odeniran and Udejaja, 2010); (Mazur and Alexander, 2001). Guru and Yadav (2019) found that economic growth is favorably and significantly correlated with domestic bank loans to the private sector. In addition to that, Puatwoe and Piabuo, (2017) also confirmed the favorable and noteworthy effects of domestic private sector lending on GDP growth. Anarfo et al. (2019) had only taken the financial sector's domestic credit as a proportion of GDP is a measure of its development, and the findings indicate that it plays a major role in driving economic growth. Besides, Chee and Nair (2010) also concluded their findings that private credit, where they meant for FDI to support economic growth, the value of private sector credits given by financial intermediaries divided by GDP is crucial. In Sri Lankan context, Fathima Rinosha and Mohamed Mustafa (2021) also proved that economic growth and private sector lending were substantially positively correlated. Thus, the researcher articulates the following hypotheses based on the above arguments and findings.

- **H1b:** Financial efficiency has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.
- **H1b₁:** Domestic credit to the private sector by banks has a significant effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.
- **H1b₂:** Claims on the private sector has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.

The researcher produced the equation that can be found here based on the literature review as follows:

$$GGDP = (BM, FSD, DCPS, CPS)$$

Where GGDP denotes Growth of Gross Domestic Product, BM denotes the ratio of Broad Money to nominal per capita GDP, FSD denotes Financial System Deposits, DCPS denotes Domestic Credit to the Private Sector, and CPS denotes Claims on the Private Sector. The empirical model of the preceding equation is described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta GGDP_t = & \alpha + \sum_{j=1}^{n1} \beta_j \Delta GGDP_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{n2} GGDP_j \Delta BM_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{n3} GGDP_j \Delta FSD_{t-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^{n4} GGDP_j \Delta DCPS_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{n5} GGDP_j \Delta CPS_{t-j} + \theta_1 GGDP_{t-1} \\ & + \theta_2 BM_{t-1} + \theta_2 FSD_{t-1} + \theta_2 DCPS_{t-1} + \theta_2 CPS_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

In order to test the research hypotheses, statistical tools are used, including Unit Root Test and Co-Integration Tests using EViews version six software package.

Results and Discussions

Stationarity testing

The unit roots are the primary cause of non-stationary. When a time series does not have a unit root, it is considered stationary; when it does, it is considered non-stationary. This suggests that one of the factors contributing to non-stationary (Nkoro and Uko, 2016). The researcher has examined the stationary properties of several variables, including GGDP, BM, CPS, FSD, and DCPS, according to the information provided. The property of a time series in which the statistical properties remain constant over time is known as stationary. In econometric modelling, stationary variables are essential because they enable the establishment of meaningful long-run relationships.

Table 2. Unit root test

Variables	Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test		Phillips-Perron unit root test	
	Level	1 st difference	Level	1 st difference
GGDP	-5.6708***	-11.3176***	-5.6138***	-26.0808***
BM	0.8672	-3.8989**	1.0617	-7.9669***
FSD	1.3683	-5.6636***	0.7354	-5.7792***
DCPS	-0.5111	-7.0936***	-0.3526	-7.1598***
CPS	-6.8934***	-7.1492***	-6.8783***	-42.5915***

Note: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.1$

Using Table 2, the researcher has determined the stationary properties of the variables. Both GGDP and CPS are stated to be stationary at both the level and the first difference. This indicates that the statistical properties of these variables do not vary over time, as do their first differences (the changes between consecutive observations). FSD and DCPS, on the other hand, are not stationary at the level (their statistical properties change over time), but they become stationary when they are subtracted once (their first differences are stationary). This indicates that the variables have unit roots, which indicates that they are integrated of order 1, also known as I(1).

Due to the different orders of integration of the variables (GGDP and CPS are I(0), while FSD and DCPS are I(1)), it may be inappropriate to use a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model or a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to ascertain the long-run relationship between the variables. Typically, VAR and VECM models presume that all variables have the same order of integration. The researcher has employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Co-Integration technique to address this issue. The ARDL model permits the examination of long-run relationships between variables whose orders of integration differ. It can account for both the short-run dynamics and the long-run equilibrium between variables. So, the researcher uses ARDL model to investigate the effect of the development of financial institutions on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka.

Long term estimates of the effect of the development of financial institutions on growth of the economy of Sri Lanka.

A long-term relationship between the variables under investigation is established by using the Bound F-statistic, which makes it possible to create a Co-Integration relationship (Nkoro and Uko, 2016). The Bound test is a useful instrument for determining whether variables are cointegrated in the short and long run. If the variables exhibit cointegration in both the short-run and long-run models, an error-correction model can be used to analyze the adjustment dynamics. If cointegration does not exist, however, the short-run ARDL model can be employed. Researchers can conclude the presence of cointegration and establish a long-term relationship by comparing the calculated F-statistic to the critical value for the upper bound I(1). In such circumstances, the null hypothesis is refuted, and the Error Correction Model for the Long Run is estimated. If the calculated F-statistic declines below the critical value for the lower bound I(0), cointegration and long-term relationships are absent. In such situations, the null hypothesis is not rejected, and short-term model estimation using the ARDL model is

performed. The test is regarded inconclusive when the F-statistic falls between the lower bound I (0) and the upper bound I(1) (Nkoro and Uko, 2016).

Table 3. ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BM	0.417367	0.151985	2.746112	0.0086
FSD	-0.184781	0.111232	-1.661214	0.1035
DCPS	-0.178274	0.089309	-1.996153	0.0519
CPS	0.292129	0.070953	4.117203	0.0002
C	-3.134715	2.443023	-1.283130	0.2059
F-Bounds Test- Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship				
Test Statistic	Value	Significance.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	8.192167	10%	2.2	3.09
k	4	5%	2.56	3.49
		2.5%	2.88	3.87
		1%	3.29	4.37

H₀: There is no Co-Integration equation

H₁: Existence of the Co-Integration equation

The F-statistic is 8.192, and the upper bound critical value at 95% confidence is 3.49. F-statistic is higher than the upper bound critical value I (1). Reject the null hypothesis. At a confidence level of 95%, a Co-Integration equation exists. The researcher concludes that a Co-Integration equation exists. It indicates the presence of a long-term relationship. Therefore, the researcher estimates the Error Correction Model to explain the short-run and long-run cointegration. In this situation, the estimations of the regression model's parameters may be accurate, resolving the spurious equation problem. The only information the regression equation provides is the short-term relationship between the variables. It offers no insight into the long-term behavior of the model's parameters. Since researchers are predominantly interested in long-term relationships between the variables under consideration, this creates a problem, and the ECM is required to solve it. The ECM specification now incorporates both long-term and short-term data.

According to the results presented in Table 3, the p-value of BM associated with the test is found to be 0.0086, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, providing evidence in favor of the alternative hypothesis. At a 95% confidence level, it can be concluded that BM has a statistically significant long-run effect on GGDP. The β coefficient corresponding to BM is estimated to be 0.417367. Thus, at a 95% confidence level, BM has a positive significant long-run effect on GGDP. This implies that as the ratio of broad money to nominal GDP per capita increases, economic growth increases in the long run. This finding complies with the findings of (Rousseau and Wachtel, 2001), who found economic growth is strongly and robustly impacted by the depth of the financial sector and Puatwoe and Piabuo (2017) also confirmed the substantial and favourable effect of broad money on economic growth.

Besides, Chee and Nair (2010) also concluded their findings that in order for FDI to support economic growth, liquid liabilities/M2 or M3 are essential.

Further, the p-value of CPS associated with the test is found to be 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, providing evidence in favor of the alternative hypothesis. At a 95% confidence level, it can be concluded that CPS has a statistically significant long-run effect on GGDP. The β coefficient corresponding to CPS is estimated to be 0.2921. Thus, at a 95% confidence level, CPS has a positive significant long-run effect on GGDP. This implies that as the Claims in the Private Sector increase, economic growth increases in the long run. Thus, it complies with the findings of some scholars. For instance: (Guru and Yadav, 2019); (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Anarfo *et al.*, 2019); (Chee and Nair, 2010); (Fathima Rinosha and Mohamed Mustafa, 2021).

Short term estimates effect of the development of financial institutions on growth of the economy of Sri Lanka.

Table 4. ARDL Error Correction Regression
 Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(BM)	0.084160	0.134949	0.623647	0.5359
D(DCPS)	-0.479977	0.240527	-1.995522	0.0518
D(DCPS(-1))	-0.388315	0.195455	-1.986720	0.0528
D(CPS)	0.152808	0.052693	2.899961	0.0057
CointEq(-1)*	-0.951260	0.128860	-7.382122	0.0000
R-squared	0.556427		Mean dependent variance	-0.003356
Adjusted R-squared	0.521636		SD dependent variance	2.479521
SE of regression	1.714932		Akaike info criterion	4.001669
Sum squared residual	149.9905		Schwarz criterion	4.182504
Log-likelihood	-107.0467		Hannan-Quinn criteria.	4.071778
Durbin-Watson stat	2.017102			

Model testing

$$D(GGDP) = -2.98 - 0.951 * GGDP(-1) + 0.397 * BM(-1) - 0.175 * FSD ** - 0.169 * DCPS(-1) + 0.277 * CPS(-1) + 0.084 * D(BM) - 0.479 * D(DCPS) - 0.388 * (GGDP - (0.417 * BM(-1) - 0.184 * FSD(-1) - 0.178 * DCPS(-1) + 0.292 * CPS(-1) - 3.134) + 0.152 * D(CPS))$$

To test if there is a long-run Co-Integration between the variables then the following hypothesis can be tested.

H₀: There is no long-run Co-Integration among variables

H₁: There is a long-run Co-Integration among variables

Based on the analysis, the p-value for CointEq (-1) is 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. At a 95% confidence level, it can be concluded that there is a long-run cointegration among the variables. The CointEq (-1) coefficient is -0.951, indicating the presence of long-run causality. CointEq (-1) represents the speed of adjustment towards equilibrium. With a value of -0.951, the speed of adjustment is significant. This implies that the variables move towards their equilibrium at a considerable rate. Specifically, the speed of adjustment is calculated as 95.1% ($0.951 * 100$).

Based on the findings presented in Table 4, the p-value of D (CPS) is 0.005, which is below the significance level of 0.05. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. At a 95% confidence level, there is evidence to suggest that the change in CPS has a significant effect on the change in GGDP. The β coefficient is 0.152, indicating D (CPS) has a significant positive effect on D (GGDP). This implies that if D (CPS) increases by 1, D (GGDP) increases by 0.152. This implies that as the Claims in the Private Sector increase, economic growth increases in the short run as well. Thus, it complies with the findings of some scholars. For instance: (Guru and Yadav, 2019); (Puatwoe and Piabuo, 2017); (Anarfo et al., 2019); (Chee and Nair, 2010); (Fathima Rinosha and Mohamed Mustafa, 2021). Thus, the researcher comes to the decision that Claims in the Private Sector should be considered as the prominent variable that has a significant positive impact on economic growth in the long run and short run as well. While Financial System Deposits to GDP (FSD) and Domestic Credit to Private Sector by banks (DCPS) got insignificant with GDP growth in both short-term and long-term may be due to their narrowed money supply than the Broad Money (BM) and Claims on Private Sector (CPS).

The *R-squared* value in Table 4 is 0.556, which indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable (the variable being predicted or explained) that can be explained by the independent variable(s) in a regression model. Approximately 55.6% of the variance in the dependent variable can be explained or predicted by the included independent variable(s). Other factors or random error account for the remaining 44.4% of the variance. Further, this model has a Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.017 (see Table 4). Since it is near 2, this suggests that the model does not reveal any significant autocorrelation.

Stability estimates

CUSUM (Cumulative Sum) and CUSUM of Square are statistical techniques used for monitoring and detecting structural changes or shifts in a time series. CUSUM is a method that involves calculating the cumulative sum of deviations from a reference value over time. It is used to monitor changes in the mean or level of a time series. Both CUSUM and CUSUM of Square are used as diagnostic tools in time series analysis to identify structural breaks, changes in the mean or variance, and deviations from stability. These techniques help researchers and analysts detect and investigate potential shifts in the underlying characteristics of the time series data.

Figure 2. Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Cumulative Sum of Square (CUSUM of Square)
 If the stability of the parameter cannot be established, the estimates obtained from the ARDL model may not be reliable. To assess the parameter stability in this study, we employed two techniques: Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Cumulative Sum of Squares (CUSUM of Square). These methods allow us to evaluate whether the recursive residuals remain within the critical boundaries defined at a 5% significance level. By examining Figure 4.2, we observe that both the CUSUM and CUSUM of Square plots of the recursive residuals behave within the defined critical bounds. This indicates that the calculated ARDL model demonstrates stability. Consequently, we can confidently affirm that the estimated ARDL model is stable based on these findings.

Sensitivity estimates

Table 5 presents the results of the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM (Lagrange Multiplier) test is used to assess the presence of serial correlation, also known as autocorrelation, in a regression model.

Table 5. Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	0.245509	Prob. F (2,44)		0.7834
Obs*R-squared	0.618035	Prob. Chi-Square(2)		0.7342
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
GGDP (-1)	0.107034	0.355457	0.301117	0.7647
BM	-0.014173	0.175750	-0.080644	0.9361
BM (-1)	-0.010035	0.170964	-0.058698	0.9535
FSD	0.016896	0.112793	0.149797	0.8816
DCPS	0.017439	0.295949	0.058925	0.9533
DCPS (-1)	0.033875	0.529282	0.064002	0.9493
DCPS (-2)	-0.046272	0.317786	-0.145607	0.8849
CPS	-0.002577	0.068879	-0.037414	0.9703
CPS (-1)	-0.014215	0.100135	-0.141958	0.8878
C	-0.102616	2.347346	-0.043716	0.9653
RESID (-1)	-0.130150	0.392379	-0.331694	0.7417
RESID (-2)	-0.097864	0.159239	-0.614575	0.5420
R-squared	0.011036	Mean dependent variance		2.301545

According to Table 5, the p-value is 0.734, and it is greater than 0.05. You cannot reject the null hypothesis and can't accept the alternative hypothesis. At a 95% confidence level, there is not enough evidence to say that this model has a Serial Correlation Error. It implies that there is no Serial Correlation Error in this model.

H₀: Model has no Serial Correlation Error

H₁: Model has a Serial Correlation Error

Table 6 presents Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey (BPG) test used to detect the presence of heteroskedasticity in a regression model.

Table 6. Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.335008	Prob. F (9,46)		0.9586
Obs*R-squared	3.444735	Prob. Chi-Square (9)		0.9440
Scaled explained SS	3.909423	Prob. Chi-Square (9)		0.9173
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	10.03607	6.682173	1.501916	0.1400
GGDP (-1)	0.135895	0.401894	0.338135	0.7368
BM	-0.552553	0.497869	-1.109835	0.2728
BM (-1)	0.181126	0.448822	0.403558	0.6884
FSD	0.023151	0.306997	0.075410	0.9402
DCPS	1.249923	0.810711	1.541760	0.1300
DCPS (-1)	-1.022757	1.208625	-0.846216	0.4018
DCPS (-2)	0.063136	0.643067	0.098179	0.9222
CPS	-0.275043	0.189941	-1.448041	0.1544
CPS (-1)	0.011409	0.195729	0.058288	0.9538

H₀: There is no heteroskedasticity

H₁: There is heteroskedasticity

According to Table 6, the p-value is 0.944, and it is greater than 0.05. You cannot reject the null hypothesis and cannot accept the alternative hypothesis. At a 95% confidence level, there is not enough evidence to say that there is heteroskedasticity. It implies that there is no heteroskedasticity error in this model.

Wald Test

Table 7. Wald Test

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	42.27105	(10, 46)	0.0000
Chi-square	422.7105	10	0.0000
Null Hypothesis: C (1) =C (2) =C(3)=C(4)=C(5)=C(6)=C(7)=C(8)=C(9)=C(10)=0			
Null Hypothesis Summary:			

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C (1)	0.048740	0.138209
C (2)	0.084160	0.171214
C (3)	0.312864	0.154347
C (4)	-0.175775	0.105574
C (5)	-0.479977	0.278799
C (6)	-0.077924	0.415639
C (7)	0.388315	0.221147
C (8)	0.152808	0.065320
C (9)	0.125083	0.067310
C (10)	-2.981929	2.297958

H₀: There is no short-run causal relationship between the dependent and independent variables

H₁: There is a short-run causal relationship between the dependent and independent variables

The researcher utilized the Wald test to assess the presence of a short-run causal relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables. After conducting the Wald test and referring to the results in Table 7, the obtained p-value is 0.000, which is smaller than the significance level of 0.05. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. With a 95% confidence level, it can be concluded that there is a significant short-run causal relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis	Result
H1 : There is a supply-leading hypothesis that exists in terms of development of financial institutions on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka	Accepted
H1a : Financial depth has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.	Accepted
H1a1 : Broad money has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.	Accepted in the long term
H1a2 : Financial system deposits have a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.	No enough evidence in favour.
H1b : Financial efficiency has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.	Accepted
H1b1 : Domestic credit to the private sector by banks has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.	No enough evidence in favour.
H1b2 : Claims on the private sector has a significant positive effect on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka in the short term and long term.	Accepted in long-term and short term

Conclusion

The main objective of the present study is to investigate the effect of the development of financial institutions on the growth of the economy of Sri Lanka, and the findings can be concluded as there is enough evidence to say that financial institutions' development has a significant positive impact in the short term and long term. Even though some of the variables employed in the study show insignificant results, Broad Money and Claims in the Private Sector were found as the most significant variables that impact economic growth in Sri Lanka. Therefore, at this country's reviving stage, if the government paid more attention to the financial efficiency of the financial institutions, the economy of the country would hit a growth rate beyond the prediction, even in the short term as well as the long term. The country officials can adopt policies to ease the monetary conditions relating to the lending and depositing facilities of financial institutions. This can induce the Claims on Private Sector, and it will stimulate the economic growth of the country as a whole. Sri Lanka has to revisit the monetary policies and change that to induce the money supply since the inflation has already been under control. Interest rates and reserve requirements can be reduced further to enhance the money circulation in the economy. Moreover, the Central Bank of Sri Lanka would make a strategic plan to focus on the financial depth of the financial institutions to experience the long-term merits in terms of economic growth. Future studies can explore a comparative study between the developing and developed countries, which can enable the countries to improve their economic growth in the short term and long term and also adopt strategies for improving financial depth and financial efficiency.

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Appendix

List of Abbreviation

The ratio of broad money to nominal per capita GDP	BM
Financial system deposits to GDP	FSD
Domestic credit to private sector by banks (% of GDP)	DCPS
Claims on private sector (annual growth as % of broad money)	CPS
GDP Growth	GGDP
ASEAN Regional Forum	ARF
Trend Stationary (deterministic) Process	TSP
Difference Stationary Process	DSP
Ordinary Least Square	OLS
Error Correction Model	ECM
Auto Regressive Distributed Lag	ARDL
Vector Auto Regressive	VAR
Vector Error Correction Model	VECM
Sequential Modified LR test statistic	LR
Final Prediction Error	FPE
Akaike Information Criterion	AIC
Schwarz information Criterion	SC
Hannan-Quinn information criterion	HQ

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